

INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE TEACHING OF SPECIALIZED SUBJECTS

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Abstract: In today's society, innovation technologies have spread to almost every field of human activity, including education. This phenomenon gained special significance within the improvement and modernization of the established educational system due to the incorporation of innovation technologies into the educational process practice. Currently, the issue of active integration and widespread application of innovative technologies in education is critical. The current study investigates learning innovation technologies in modern education.

Keywords: education, learning, pedagogical innovation theory, learning technologies, technological approach in education, innovation educational technologies.

INTRODUCTION

The theory of innovation in education is a new field of scientific pedagogic knowledge; it is a paradigm of inseparable unity and interconnection of the three main pedagogic processes in the field of education: the creation of novelties, their mastery, and application. In other words, the study of the integration of development, mastery, and integration of novelties is the subject of innovation theory. In education, innovation theory refers to the innovative process in the educational system, as well as the innovative activity, novelty, and innovative environment in which the innovative processes take place. Innovative processes are examined from three perspectives: social-economic, psychological, and organizational-regulatory. These factors define the overall climate and conditions under which innovative processes occur and which either prevent or facilitate the process. Furthermore, the innovative process is consciously regulated rather than being spontaneous. Integrating novelties is a significant new management function.

Innovative technologies have transformed the way we teach and learn, particularly in specialized subjects. With the advancements in technology, educators have been able to incorporate new tools and techniques to make learning more accessible, engaging, and effective. In this essay, we will explore some of the most innovative technologies used in the teaching of specialized subjects.

One of the most significant ways in which technology has changed the teaching of specialized subjects is through the use of online learning platforms. Online learning has become increasingly popular in recent years, particularly in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. These platforms provide students with access to a wealth of resources, including video lectures, digital textbooks, interactive quizzes, and virtual labs. Online learning has made it possible for students to access educational materials from anywhere in the world, at any time of day, and at their own pace. This level of flexibility has been particularly beneficial for students who may have other commitments, such as work or family, that would otherwise prevent them from pursuing higher education.

One of the advantages of online learning platforms is the ability to provide personalized learning experiences for each student. For example, an online platform may use algorithms to track a student's progress and tailor content to their learning style and level of understanding.

This type of personalized learning can be particularly effective in specialized subjects, where students may require different levels of support and guidance to succeed. Personalized learning can also help students stay engaged and motivated, as they can work at their own pace and receive feedback in real-time.

Another way in which technology has impacted the teaching of specialized subjects is through the use of gamification. Gamification refers to the integration of game-like elements into the learning process. This technology has been particularly effective in engaging students who may otherwise be disinterested in a particular subject. For example, a gamified lesson on math could involve solving problems to advance to the next level, earning rewards for correct answers, and competing against other students in a virtual classroom. This type of interactive and immersive learning experience can be particularly effective for younger students who are used to playing games on their phones and tablets.

Gamification has proven to be an effective tool in the teaching of specialized subjects such as coding and computer science. In these subjects, students are required to learn abstract concepts that can be difficult to understand. Gamification can help students understand complex concepts by breaking them down into smaller, more manageable tasks. By completing these tasks, students can see their progress and gain a sense of accomplishment, which can help them stay motivated and engaged.

Another innovative technology that has had a significant impact on the teaching of specialized subjects is virtual and augmented reality. Virtual and augmented reality refer to computer-generated simulations that provide an immersive experience for the user. In education, these technologies have been used to create virtual labs, simulations, and interactive 3D models. For example, a student studying biology could use virtual reality to explore the human body in 3D, while a student studying architecture could use augmented reality to visualize building designs in real-world settings. This type of technology has made it possible for students to experience concepts and ideas in a way that was previously impossible, allowing for a deeper understanding of complex subjects.

Virtual and augmented reality has been particularly useful in the teaching of specialized subjects that require hands-on experience, such as medicine, engineering, and architecture. These technologies can provide students with a safe and controlled environment to practice their skills and develop their understanding of complex concepts. By providing students with a more realistic and engaging experience, virtual and augmented reality can help students retain information and develop a deeper understanding of specialized subjects.

Innovative activity is nothing more than a set of steps taken to provide an innovative process at a specific level of education. Novelties in education manifest as the creative exploration of new ideas and principles, which, in some cases, leads to them becoming typical projects containing the conditions for their adaptation and application. There are pedagogical, supplying, and administrative novelties categorized by activity type. Innovative phenomena are classified into two types: pedagogical innovation theory (innovations in the educational system) and innovative learning. While pedagogical innovation theory is concerned with restructuring and modifying, improving and changing the educational system or its individual parts, characteristics, and aspects (creating new legal acts, new structure, models, learning paradigms, forms of integration connections, etc.), innovation learning is defined as a specific type of knowledge mastering and as a product of conscious, goal-oriented, and scientifically-

founded activity in the educational process. Innovative learning is currently taking the place of supportive learning. It is regarded as the educational system's reaction to the society's transition to a higher stage of development and to the changed educational goals. Learning that stimulates innovative changes in the existing culture and social environment is referred to as innovative learning. It acts as an active reaction to the problem situations that confront each individual and society as a whole. It is called to prepare not only a "learning person", but also a "acting person". Furthermore, all supporting learning elements are present in the innovative process; the only question is how to define the proportion of reproductive and productive, active and creative components.

Artificial intelligence (AI) is another innovative technology that has changed the way specialized subjects are taught. AI refers to the ability of machines to perform tasks that would typically require human intelligence, such as natural language processing and decision-making. In education, AI has been used to develop personalized learning experiences for students. For example, an AI-powered chatbot could answer students' questions and provide personalized feedback based on their learning styles and performance. AI has also been used to automate grading and feedback, which saves teachers time and provides students with immediate feedback on their work.

As a result, the ambiguity of many problems in teachers' professional preparation for using innovative pedagogic technologies in teaching students, as well as the definition of teachers' innovation activity per se, flaws in college education, the lack of a theory and system of professional technological preparation in pedagogic colleges, and the emerging need to develop a new approach in teachers' education define the scientific significance of the current study. The development of theoretical and practical aspects of teachers' professional preparation for using innovative pedagogic technologies would not only aid in the improvement of teachers' pedagogical proficiency, but would also have a direct positive impact on the educational process in a modern general-education school.

Finally, social media has become an important tool for teaching specialized subjects. Social media platforms such as Twitter, Facebook, and Instagram provide a space for teachers and students to share ideas, resources, and information. These platforms can be particularly useful for discussing current events and sharing news articles and research papers. Social media can also be used to create virtual classrooms, where students can participate in discussions and collaborate on projects.

In conclusion, innovative technologies have had a significant impact on the teaching of specialized subjects. Online learning platforms, gamification, virtual and augmented reality, artificial intelligence, and social media are just a few examples of how technology has changed the way we teach and learn. As technology continues to evolve, we can expect to see even more innovative tools and techniques that will revolutionize education and make learning more accessible, engaging, and effective for all students.

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